

ECOSPORT: AN INTEGRATED RECREATIONAL SPORTS PARK AT ALDERSGATE COLLEGE

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ABSTRACT

Designing Sports facilities at Aldersgate College, aimed at optimizing space usage, functionality, and engagement while promoting physical, mental, and social well-being. We all know that leisure sport is universal to all, therefore, the public has a high participation. Life lies in movement, and along with the continuous development of health consciousness, sport exercise has become one indispensable part of our life. The research focuses on creating a multifunctional sports facility that integrates sustainability, inclusivity, and biophilic design principles. By optimizing space usage and fostering a positive, engaging environment, the facility is intended to promote student development, creativity, active learning and outdoor areas designed for both fitness and relaxation, optimizing space usage to meet diverse needs. The study adopts a mixed-methods approach to data gathering, including design evaluation, case study analysis, Site visit and participatory design methods. Findings indicate that the proposed inclusive sports facility will not only improve physical accessibility but also to provide a valuable insight for future projects aimed at designing sports facilities that foster learning, engagement, and community development. This research integrates various architectural approaches to create a multifunctional space that has sustainable and inclusive environment. Ultimately, the facility will contribute to creating a more engaged and healthy community, strengthening the role of sports in the educational experience and promoting well-rounded student growth.

Keywords: sports facility design, space optimization, sustainability, inclusivity, biophilic design, student well-being, physical and mental health, community engagement, active learning, multifunctional spaces, educational architecture

INTRODUCTION

The development of university sports facilities dates back to the early 20th century, when physical education became part of the curriculum to promote student health, well-being, and discipline. As universities grew, encouraging a healthy lifestyle became essential to balance academic life. In recent decades, the Philippines has shown a strong drive to improve sports infrastructure, fueled by its passionate sports culture. Modern facilities are being built not only to reflect this enthusiasm but also to meet the growing demand for versatile venues that support various sports and foster community engagement.

In Region 2, particularly the Cagayan Valley, popular sports like basketball, volleyball, and running highlight the need for well-designed facilities. With increasing health awareness, physical activity has become a vital part of daily life. As Zhao and Bai (2014) noted, "Life lies in movement," making sports a universal and indispensable activity.

This proposal outlines the development of ECOSPORTS, a recreational sports park designed to enhance student well-being at Aldersgate College. The facility will feature a gymnasium, sports complex, and additional spaces such as a sports park with exercise areas, meditation zones, and gathering spots. The project aims to promote physical health, reduce stress, and support mental well-being by providing access to modern fitness equipment and various sports courts and fields. It will also serve as a training ground for aspiring athletes, offering resources for skill development and opportunities to compete in local, provincial, and national events. Hosting inter-school and provincial competitions will elevate the college's reputation and foster school spirit. The inclusion of mindfulness and relaxation areas supports students' mental health, helping them manage academic

and extracurricular pressures. Overall, ECOSPORTS will be a holistic space that encourages a healthy, active, and balanced student lifestyle.

Importance of Sports Facilities in School

Sports facilities play a vital role in college students' overall development by promoting physical, mental, and emotional well-being. While academics form the foundation of college life, sports offer key benefits like improved health, reduced stress, and enhanced confidence (Zia-ul-islam, 2018; Bailey, 2006; Vail, 2007). They also foster inclusivity and cross-cultural understanding by bringing together students from diverse backgrounds. Regular physical activity boosts energy, memory, and academic performance, while providing a supportive environment for personal growth. For many students, sports are a source of motivation, connection, and life skills. Investing in sports facilities is investing in students' holistic success both in college and beyond.

Inclusive Sports Facilities

Inclusive design in sports facilities focuses on creating environments where individuals of all abilities can participate and enjoy physical activity together. While events like the Paralympics and Special Olympics highlight this, true inclusion means everyone—regardless of ability, age, or gender—can join in. Modern facilities feature accessible entrances, adaptive equipment, sensory-friendly spaces, and smart technologies like digital wayfinding and adjustable sports gear. These features go beyond compliance, aiming to foster equality and community. In schools, inclusive sports parks not only support physical health but also enhance mental well-being and academic performance by offering diverse spaces for exercise, relaxation, and social interaction.

The Biophilic Approach in Designing School Sports Facility

Sustainability plays a key role in sports facility design, with biophilic design promoting well-being, performance, and faster recovery—especially valuable for student athletes (Joe Celentano, 2016). At Liberty University, the Academic and Performance Center was built to support academics, training, and health, but evolved to prioritize wellness and place-making. A central atrium brings in natural light and connects key areas, enhancing the body-mind-spirit experience. Biophilic features like daylight, water elements, indoor plants, and natural materials make the space more than functional—it becomes a nurturing, inspiring environment. As Gaston et al. (2023) note, these designs boost creativity, productivity, and overall well-being.

Evaluation of Framework

The framework shown below will aid in yielding and organizing the variables that will influence the research on creating a sports facility at Aldersgate College. It provides a clear visual representation of how the project will be implemented and the expected outcomes, ensuring that all key aspects are taken into account throughout the research process.

Figure 1
Conceptual Framework

Statement of the Problem

The chief concern of this study is to plan the architectural design of the sports facilities in Aldersgate College, the proponents of this research aim to explore specific aspects of how the design and layout of these facilities impact their usage, functionality, and overall contribution to student development. The following questions are intended to gather relevant data to support a detailed analysis:

1. How can the sports facilities be properly arranged within confined space?
2. How can architectural design be optimized to create sustainable, inclusive, and multifunctional sports facilities that meet the diverse needs of students and athletes?
3. What strategies can be used to address environmental issues in the site?

Objective of the Study

Campus Plan

To design a comprehensive campus plan for the new Aldersgate College campus in Aurora, Quezon, was the main goal of the project. It includes the principles of biophilic architecture to carefully construct and arrange spaces that put students at the very core of the design. Through carefully planned educational and sports facilities and strategically integrated natural elements, its goal is to create a productive and healthy learning environment that enhances student performance. The campus strives to foster a sense of wellbeing, lessen stress, and encourage active learning by integrating nature into the built environment. Green spaces, outdoor study places, and environmentally friendly infrastructure are all part of the design, which promotes both academic achievement and overall development. In order to keep the campus flexible to future educational demands while maintaining a close connection to its natural setting, accessibility, flexibility, and environmental sustainability are essential elements. In addition to enhancing the overall educational experience, this approach fosters creativity, collaboration, and a deep respect for the natural world. Specifically, the design objectives are as follows:

1. To design the extension campus plan from a farmland into an educational institution that can accommodate sports facilities and other amenities.
2. To conceptualized an educational campus site development plan that integrates the natural surroundings, well-designed buildings, modern facilities, and sustainable open spaces to optimize student opportunities and promote social interaction, academic progress, and physical well-being.
3. To design an integrated landscape plan that effectively integrates passive, active, and inclusive areas, encouraging social interaction, physical activity, and leisure while creating a safe, engaging, and sustainable learning environment for all users.

Sports facility Building

The project aimed to provide inclusive design for a sports facility in the Aldersgate College-Aurora Campus that will house a track and field, recreational sports park, and gymnasium with lecture rooms for the stakeholders. In accordance with the campus's overall goals, the project will additionally incorporate essential biophilic approaches that will improve students' physical and healthy educational experiences and foster an environment that is conducive to learning, creativity, and even relaxation.

1. To design a comprehensive learning environment for students by promoting socialization, psychological well-being, and physical fitness through the use of multisport courts, outdoor courts, a fitness park, and cutting-edge exercise equipment.
2. To design an inclusive design, the gymnasium will be a flexible space for sports, events, quarters, and educational activities.
3. The grandstand will feature adaptable seating, while athlete quarters provide resting areas during tournaments, as well as accommodation for competitors to maximizing usability. Additionally, the facility will include an oval with track and a designated warm up area. A fitness park will be incorporated to improve training and leisure options.
4. To conceptualized a facility that can serve as an athlete's quarters and evacuation center in times of emergency.

Significance of the Study

The study redounds to the benefit of the following individuals and sectors:

1. **Students** – The primary beneficiaries, as the facility will provide a safe and well-equipped environment for physical education, training, and competitive sports, fostering their athletic skills, teamwork, and overall well-being.
2. **Faculty and Staff** – Teachers and staff members will benefit from access to wellness programs and recreational activities, promoting a healthier work environment and encouraging work-life balance.
3. **School Athletes and Sports Teams** – The design will support school athletes by offering high-quality training spaces, enabling them to improve their performance and compete effectively in inter-school tournaments.
4. **Local Community** – The facility can serve as a venue for community sports events and recreational activities, encouraging engagement, fitness, and social interaction among residents.

5. **The College** – Alders Gate College will benefit from improved infrastructure, which can enhance its reputation, attract more students, and provide opportunities for hosting events that can generate additional funding and partnerships.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

To solve the problem, this study took a realistic approach with a descriptive and exploratory approach. It focuses on addressing real-world problems by gathering data from the field (site visits) and developing practical solutions allowing the facts to inform the conclusions. After gathering the data, the researchers examined it to Assess the viability of the proposed solution. In addition, input and recommendations from affiliated professions are sought.

In Conclusion, using technical insights from authoritative sources, the researcher developed a detailed plan for carrying out the appropriate design solution, ensuring the integrity and authenticity of the data collected throughout the research process, as well as compliance with all relevant regulations and standards.

Research Locale

Macro Locale

The Republic of the Philippines established the municipality of Quezon, Nueva Vizcaya. Act of June 18, 1961, No. 3427. Residents of Nueva Vizcaya's Quezon joined the november 12, 1963, saw the election of its Municipal District Mayor and members of the Municipal District according on division or class. Five years later, right after the municipal elections, it was officially recognised as of Nueva Vizcaya. Then, its original barangays were Caliat, Baresbes, Maddiangat, Nalubbunan, Buliwao, and Darubba. Afterward, on November 12, 1967, it established the new barangays of Runruno, Maasin, Calaocan, Bonifacio, and Aurora.

There are currently 12 barangays in the municipality; Barangay Dagupan was the final one. was established in 1979. Aurora is a barrio in Nueva Vizcaya's Quezon municipality. This amounts to 6.77% of Quezon's total population. The population of Aurora grew to 1,628 in 2020 from 640 in 1990. From the 1,578-person former population in 2015, the latest census data in 2020 reveals that this population is 0.66% more. Barangay Aurora is located at roughly 16.4903, 121.2641. At those coordinates, the elevation of this place is estimated to be 866.8 feet, or 264.2 meters. higher than the mean sea level.

The proposed project is located on an agricultural property that is presently owned and operated by Aldersgate College Inc. at Aldersgate Street, Barangay Aurora, Quezon, Nueva Vizcaya. The location is distinguished by its proximity to significant features, such as a hanging bridge to the

Figure 2
Municipality of Quezon Administrative Map

Source: LGU-Quezon

north and Buliwao Creek, which flows through the project lot. The site's rural and peaceful setting is further enhanced by the numerous farms and residential neighborhoods that surround it.

Data Gathering Procedure

Gathering information indicated a possible project that could benefit from solutions for architectural design. This data-gathering process describes the methods that are used to get pertinent data regarding a sports facility's utilization, effectiveness, and user satisfaction. The information gathered will be used to evaluate the facility's operation and identify areas in requiring development.

1. The topic of the study was chosen. The proposal was presented by the researcher's thesis adviser is. Binbinon, Tomas B. Jr. By accomplishing this, the Aldersgate College Aurora Campus was selected as the location for the thesis project. The goal is to develop a campus layout for the school and a sports facility that could support the institution's goal of improving students' physical and mental health as well as their sense of belonging and dedication to growth and excellence.
2. The researcher conducted case studies in national (Rizal Memorial Coliseum-Malate, Metro Manila) and local (Central Luzon State University-Muñoz, Campus, Isabela

State University, Ilagan Sports Complex-Ilagan City, Isabela, Isabela Sports Complex-Ilagan City, Isabela, Cabatuan Sports Coliseum-Cabatuan, Isabela)

3. The researcher conducted an interview with Engr. Godofredo M. Batarao, Jr., RCE, RGE, along with Engr. Angelito G. Capuno, RME, MBA, and also the staff of the planning and design team of Aldersgate College.
4. The researcher analyzed the proposal of sports facilities through the data collected such as number of annual enrollees and overall population, booking records, and maintenance reports, It will be reviewed to determine structures in the utilization of the facility, the generation of income, and maintenance issues.
5. Researcher need to make an attempt to gather papers that contain topics like official or unofficial documents, financial and budget data, visualizations, guidelines, and conversation. This is transformed into official plans, zoning bylaws, site plan control guidelines, staff and consultant reports, documents and correspondence, personal interview notes and records, plans, and site development plan.

Figure 9

Current Situations of the Aldersgate College Aurora Campus

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Market Study

Demand Supply and Analysis

Aldersgate Sports Facility plays a vital role in both the school and the wider community by fostering inclusivity and encouraging physical activity. It provides students with a dedicated space to

exercise, promoting health and well-being while also serving as a hub for building camaraderie. By bringing together students from diverse cultural backgrounds, the facility creates opportunities for them to connect, share experiences, and work towards common goals. This shared environment helps students develop teamwork, communication, and leadership skills, while also strengthening the bond between the school and the community through events and activities that bring everyone together. Ultimately, the Aldersgate Sports Facility is not just a place for physical activity, but a space that nurtures personal growth and community cohesion.

Marketing Program

Aldersgate College, as company, aims to foster sports interest in students, staff, and the schools by providing outstanding facilities that put an emphasis on accessibility, inclusivity, and wellbeing. The institution is the perfect place for physical development and well-being because of its state-of-the-art sports facilities, which support a variety of sports and fitness activities. In order to encourage a healthy, active lifestyle for all of its members, Aldersgate College provides wellness-focused initiatives, inclusive programs, and accessibility. Faculty and staff, and local sports teams may all take access to these exceptional facilities in addition to the college's ongoing efforts to increase its target audience and improve connections within the institution through clever digital marketing and exciting events. In accordance with the school's objective of promoting academic and personal development through a comprehensive approach to health and wellness, the program's effectiveness will be measured by measures such as increased involvement, engagement, and long-term progress.

Several effective marketing strategies for the aldersgate sports facilities include the following:

A. **Digital Marketing:** Establish a distinct website for the school with details about its schedule, programs, facilities, and reservation policies. Additionally, to involve students, instructors, staff, and others, create accounts on Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter and run social media campaigns. Emails can also notify staff, instructors, and students about forthcoming events, class schedules, exclusive offers, and success stories in weekly or monthly newsletters.

B. **School Events and Competitions:** Plan campus-wide activities that involve both students and faculty, such as intramural competitions, sports days, and fitness challenges. The school can encourage others to host important events like physical development classes, competitions, and encouragement assemblies at the sports complex. Along with attracting sponsorships and potential partnerships, funding will be provided for collaboration with other professionals in sports, events, and training.

C. **Printed Materials:** Although the digital marketing platform has made the biggest contribution, printed materials continue to have a big impact on the school sports facility's promotion. Brochures, fliers, and posters should be distributed in neighboring schools, community centers, and sporting activities. Materials that describe the special qualities and advantages of the programs the facility offers should be both aesthetically attractive as well as higher education.

D. **Engagement of Alumni.** Maintaining relationships with its alumni is also crucial because they can serve as ambassadors of the programs the school offers. In order to encourage present and prospective students, alumni could be approached via newsletters, events, and social media to share their professional athletic success stories. Alumni can also be a valuable source of critical criticism and support for the sports facility's programs, which will help them become more relevant and effective.

3.2 Calendar of Activities

The problem with school sports facilities is that their relevance is contingent on when there is schedule of events in school. These sports events and school activities should be designed to align with the calendar throughout the school year. If no events are taking place, the facilities could be vacant or open for general student use, but the main purpose is to support the planned sports activities.

3.3 Technical Study

Site Analysis

Figure 11

Views Surrounding the Site

The proposed school sports facilities are located on a site within Barangay Aurora, Quezon, Nueva Vizcaya, a municipality in the Philippines' Cagayan Valley region. The town of Quezon is rich in history and cultural diversity, and it is mostly an agricultural town. The municipality is home to some of the most fertile areas in the area, supporting a wide range of crops such as corn, rice, and various fruits and vegetables. The project site is situated in Barangay Aurora, a rural town in the center of Quezon. Quezon has a tropical climate with distinct dry and wet seasons. November through April is the dry season, and May through October is the wet season. The average annual temperature is between 25°C and 32°C, with April and May being the hottest months and July and August being the wettest.

Farms and plantations may be seen nearby the project site, which is located in the center of a largely agricultural neighborhood. The Cagayan River, which flows along Quezon, Nueva Vizcaya's eastern border, offers a sufficient supply of water for farming purposes, including irrigation. Because the ecosystem is home to numerous species of fish, birds, and wildlife, the creek's existence also enhances biodiversity.

Aldersgate College's sports complex is in a prime location, adjacent to the town hall and conveniently accessible by car. Students and the local population will find it easy to get to due to its central location in the town. It is an ideal location for physical activity, sports, and community events

due to its convenient access to business entities, public transportation, and town facilities. This helps the college draw a wide variety of participants and fortify its relationships with the community.

Site Location

Figure 12

Site Location Satellite View

Topography and Contour

As shown in the figures below, the project site's terrain is unusually flat, with numerous neighboring hills of various slopes.

Figure 13

Site Location Slope Satellite View

Map 1

Topographic Map of Quezon, Nueva Vizcaya

Climate

The wet seasons in Quezon, Nueva Vizcaya, are brief, pleasant, humid, and somewhat cloudy, while the dry seasons are hot, oppressive, and overcast. The average temperature is between 65°F and 90°F throughout the year; it hardly ever drops below 61°F or rises beyond 95°F.

Data indicates that the hot season, which lasts from April 6 to July 13, lasts 3.2 months and has average daily high temperatures of over 88°F. June is the hottest month in Quezon, with highs of 90°F and lows of 72°F on average. In contrast, the 2.6-month cool season, which runs from

Figure 14

Climate Chart of Quezon, Nueva Vizcaya

Source: WeatherSpark

November 28 to February 16, with daily highs that are typically lower than 82°F. January is the coldest month in Quezon, with highs of 80°F and lows of 65°F on average.

SWOT Analysis

Strength

1. **The location is strategically located.** Due to its close proximity to the municipal building, the sports facility serves as the main venue for local engagement and school sports programs, making it easily accessible to both locals and visitors.
2. **Lack of competition.** Because Quezon does not currently have any sports facilities, this facility would close a significant need in the community. It is also perfect for the school and the children, giving them a chance to encourage physical activity and wellness.
3. **Easy construction is made possible by flat terrain.** Because of the site's level terrain, less work will need to be done on minor grading or land leveling. Building infrastructure and structures may become simpler as a result, and a project may save money, time, and complexity.

Weakness

1. **Initial investment.** Building a sports facility in an agricultural region might require a large maintenance, equipment, and building investment, which could be costly.
2. **Limited awareness.** Since Quezon lacks a sports culture or facilities, it could be necessary to use intensive marketing campaigns to inform the locals of the advantages and opportunities that are accessible.
3. **A residential plot is located in the site's center.** The overall layout and operation of the campus may be affected by residential plots in the middle. It could create obstacles to unified planning and development, which would make it difficult to integrate various campus regions. In addition to restricting the institute's potential for growth, these central residential plots would make it difficult to plan the appropriate infrastructure and access points.

Opportunity

1. **Due to the lack of local sports facilities.** There is an exceptional opportunity to establish a unique sports and fitness location in the area that will serve students and employees, aspiring athletes and trainers, and hold events and other competitions.
2. **Participation of students, athletes, and staff.** The facility could offer sports activities, developing student talent and encouraging sustained physical exercise.
3. **No comparable chances in the community offered by any other educational institution.** It has a special place and importance in the community because there are not many other organizations with comparable sporting facilities. Students and aspiring athletes may be drawn to the facilities for training because of their distinctiveness.
4. **Corporate support.** The facility's development may be aided by government subsidies, locally based business sponsorships, and public-private partnerships due to its advantageous position close to the town hall.

Threat

1. **Conflicts over land usage could occur nearby.** Conflicts over land use between housing, education, and agriculture may hinder peaceful growth, cause delays in zoning and planning, and result in legal issues. To balance interests in these conflicts, careful discussion and strategic planning are needed.

2. **Difficulties in providing roads on the property.** It might be difficult to build a sufficient road network because of the residential lot in the center of the property. These homes might make it difficult to build the infrastructure that is required, which would impair campus access and connectivity.

3.4 User Behavioral Analysis

User behavioral analysis is highly important in architecture when designing and planning spaces. By understanding how users interact, it ensures that the space adapts to the needs of its users, encouraging positive interactions and creating a design that is efficient and functional, in addition to a sense of connection within the built environment.

This study, which relates to the study of Gumayagay (2016), analyzes user behavior in sports facilities. In this analysis, there are three main users of the school sports complex: the primary, which include spectators; the secondary user, which includes athletes; and the tertiary user, which includes students and instructors. This study drew a detailed representation of how these users behave during sports events and regular school days. This analysis makes a valuable contribution to space planning and architectural conceptualization. Thus, it is necessary to understand the distinct needs and behaviors of each user group

CONCLUSION

- The primary design objectives were to transform a college farm lot into ensure efficiency for stakeholders, improve the learning experience, and provide an optimal learning atmosphere.
- The study focused on designing the new Aldersgate College Campus Plan in Aurora, Quezon, specifically in connection to designing a recreational sports facility.
- The project's goal was to design an innovative, sustainable, and integrative campus with the surrounding community, in addition, to taking into account a focus on flexibility and safety risks in design, as well as well-planned structures and methods.
- This study adds to the ongoing discussion about inclusive campus infrastructure, providing findings that can help guide future improvements in sports facility planning. While the proposed design addresses fundamental inclusion problems, additional study is needed to investigate new trends in adaptive sports technologies and user-specific demands in order to improve accessibility and engagement even further.
- The study emphasized the necessity of universal design, adaptable sports infrastructure, and strategic space planning in accommodating people with various abilities, backgrounds, and interests. By including inclusive design aspects such as barrier-free access, multi-purpose sports facilities, and assistive technology, the proposed facility hopes to build a more egalitarian and engaged campus community.
- The research underlined the relevance investing in an inclusive sports facility is an investment in the university's future, helping to create a more dynamic, engaged, and well-rounded student body while confirming the institution's commitment to holistic education and inclusivity.
- The findings underline that an accessible sports facility encourages not just physical accessibility but also social inclusion, mental well-being, and a sense of belonging among students and instructors. Sports facilities play a crucial role in providing spaces that encourage participation in sports and leisure activities, highlighting the importance of thoughtful, user-centered design.

Recommendations

- The researcher recommends that the proponent consult that future development and design of sports facilities include early and continuous consultation with structural engineers and allied professionals.
- It is also recommended a more in-depth study to provide detailed data on the potential volume of rainwater that can be harvested and how much water consumption can be reduced in the facility.

Design Concept

The design concept of the project is creating inclusive space for the school to promote physical exercise while developing stronger social relationships, enhancing inclusivity, and deepening the connection with the natural environment. This concept aims to be a center for education and serves as a training ground for aspiring athletes. Encourage students and diverse community members of all ages to engage in sports and outdoor activities to thrive together.

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